

Tribological effects due to different geometries of surface texturing on lubricated point contacts

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Abstract

This paper presents a study of textured patterns on friction behaviour of lubricated point contacts. The tribological investigation under point contact was focused on the effect of the shape of textured pattern and laser-texturing parameters—including the dimple depth and size, the dimple area density and the contact size on the coefficient of friction under different lubrication regimes, achieved by varying the sliding speed and the lubricant viscosity. Experiments have been conducted on a MCR-301-Ball-on-three plate tribometer, where steel ball was used to slide against steel plate samples with or without textures. A pure Poly-Alpha-Olefin oil was used to lubricate the contacts. Three types of laser-textured patterns of micro-cavities were studied with two different viscosities. It was found that, in comparison with smooth steel surfaces, the laser-texturing significantly reduced friction and wear in the mixed regime, with a low viscosity lubricant. In contrary, the smooth surface tested with a high viscosity lubricant provides a better friction reduction as compared to the textured geometries, during the transition from the mixed to hydrodynamic regime. Effects of the change in the temperature was studied with smooth samples by using low viscosity lubricant. Pressure measurement tests were performed to measure the hertzian contact area, where we found for the textured geometries were having much smaller contact area as compared to the than smooth surfaces.

Keywords: Surface Texturing, Friction Reduction, femtosecond Laser ablation, lubrication, tribometer

1. Introduction

It has been known for decades that topography of rubbing surfaces has major influences on their frictional behaviour. The complexity of the tribological properties of materials and the economic aspects of friction and wear justify an increasing research effort. There is an increasing need to reduce and control friction and wear in order to extend the lifetime of mechanical systems, to improve their efficiency and reliability, to conserve scarce material resources and energy as well as to improve safety [1].

The surface topography can also be changed in a very controllable way by introducing small dimples or channels known as surface texturing. The use of the textured surface to reduce friction probably only started in 1966 [22] when Hamilton proposed a theory to explain the extra hydrodynamic pressure generated by micro-irregularities on mechanical seals working under parallel sliding lubrication conditions. The research in textured surfaces for friction reduction only widely started from 1996 when Etsion's group showed significant effects of textured surface through the modelling of textured surfaces [23]. Over the past 20 years, over 400 papers have been published reporting studies on surface texturing, covering both experimental and theoretical investigations [24]. There are different research groups in the world, which are continuously implementing new theories into the real experiments by employing micro-surface patterning methods to texture tribological surfaces, including vibrorolling (1984- Schneider), reactive ion etching (Wang-2003) and others (Etsion-2005 (state of the art) [25]). However, Laser Surface Texturing (LST) in particular has emerged in recent years as a viable option of surface engineering resulting in significant improvement in load capacity, wear resistance, friction coefficient etc. of tribological mechanical components. LST consists of creating an array of high-density micro-dimples on a metal surface by laser ablation and each of these micro-dimples can serve either as a micro-hydrodynamic bearing in cases of full or mixed lubrication, a micro-reservoir for lubricant in cases of starved lubrication conditions, or a micro-trap for wear debris in either lubricated or dry sliding [2,3]. The advantages of using femtosecond laser pulses compared to nanosecond ones reside in the fact that the ablation process is substantially melting free. Therefore, no burrs create on the edges of the micro-dimples, which could be detrimental to the desired tribological behavior, and no further polishing of the surfaces is required after LST. Furthermore, femtosecond laser ablation allows finely control the depth and the geometry of the dimples with micrometer precision [4].

Understanding of the lubrication regimes, in which our machines run is essential to choose the best viscosity and type of lubricant with the target to avoid wear and improve energy saving. The benefit arising from cavities or grooves on a flat surface is a combination of several effects improving oil supply and reducing abrasion in the sliding contact: surface cavities or grooves can act as oil reservoirs, which transport or retain oil to be released in emergency situations. Cavities, grooves and valleys in the surface can disarm wear particles by entrapping them, thereby suppressing abrasion and ploughing friction. When surface irregularities appear at sufficient density, they can improve the wetting of the surface by an oil [26,27], and thereby support the lubricating oil film formation. At higher sliding speed, and with a sufficient supply of oil, individual surface cavities may act as hydrodynamic pressure pockets, which reduce friction, unless the benefit is counteracted by turbulence or cavitation at the cavities. A drawback of the surface irregularities may occur as abrasive wear of a soft counter surface at

high contact pressure [28]. LST was observed to expand the range of the hydrodynamic lubrication regime in terms of load and sliding speed for both high- and low- viscosity oil lubricants [12]

The aim of the present research work is to study the effects of different textured geometrical pattern with a variety of dimensions and distributions of micro-dimples in point contact. The influence of several geometric parameters, such as the contact length, cavity depth and width, on the drag force has been studied. A thorough analysis of the density, viscosity of the lubricant, directional alignment of the samples and Hertzian contact pressure is provided, showing how these quantities are influenced by the geometry of the surface micro-texturing under low and high viscosity conditions. Furthermore, the temperature loop and pressure distribution tests highlights that different trends exist, depending upon the geometry of the textured samples and their behavior in different regime, due to which a different flow dynamics occurs and the cavities have a different influence on the drag force during point contact in the lubrication regime.

2. Experimental Setup

2.1 Surface texturing by Femtosecond laser ablation (fsLA)

The fabrication was performed upon the samples [stainless steel-polished (1.4112)] provided by R&D from Bosch, Stuttgart. Microtexturing was performed by using an ultrafast fiber CPA laser system (mod. Sci-series from Active Fiber Systems GmbH), delivering 650 fs pulses, with a maximum laser power of 50 W, a wavelength of 1030 nm, a pulse energy up to 100 μ J and a repetition rate ranging from 50 KHz to 10 MHz. The high level of accuracy and reproducibility of the ablated micro-features, only achieved by working at near threshold laser fluence. The linearly polarized beam coming from the laser source was firstly converted into circularly polarized light through a quarter-wave plate, to prevent anisotropic absorption on the ablating surface and, after passing through a suitable beam expander, directed towards a 14-mm aperture galvo-scan head (mod. HurryScan from ScanLab GmbH) equipped with a 100-mm focal length F-Theta lens.

Figure 1: Active Fiber System Laser

A laser trepanning technique was employed to ablate the material for the formation of designed geometrical pattern on the sample surfaces (Table 1). The diameters and depths of the structures were precisely controlled by finely adjusting the laser parameters, and the beam scanning path.

We operated the laser at the lowest achievable repetition rate of 50 kHz with variable average power in the range from 40 to 60 mW. The trepanning speed of the laser beam and the hatching used in each geometry was varied according to the required parameters for each geometry. Table 1. summarizes the parameters defined for each texture geometry.

Table 1: Description of the sample parameters

Types of Textured Geometry	Dimension (μm)	Dimension of dimples and spacing between adjacent quasi rectangles & Density = ρ (μm)	Track depth (μm)
Hexagonal	545(D)	Circle = 183 ρ= 27 %	6.6
Triangular	325(S)	Circle = 183 ρ= 29 %	6.7
Rectangular	200(L),100(W)	Vertical = 50 & Horizontal = 50 ρ= 53 %	7.3

After the fsLA process, the morphology of the fabricated micro-features was characterized by optical and scanning electron microscopy as well as using a white light confocal microscope by CSM-Instruments, with lateral and vertical resolution of, respectively, 1.1 μm and 0.005 μm. Table 2. shows an overall view of the worked area acquired with an optical microscope. The machined part is completely free from melting and burrs, due to the high level of accuracy provided by the ultrashort pulse duration ablation regime, together with the near threshold laser fluence selected for the LST process. Therefore, no further polishing was required after laser micro-machining [2,3,4,20]. The optical microscope analysis confirmed that the parameters of the textured geometries meet the required specifics with a micrometer precision, as confirmed in Table 2.

2.2. Characterization

The tribological properties of the textured samples were evaluated using a Rheometer MCR-301, at the research facilities of the Robert Bosch GmbH in Renningen, Stuttgart, Germany. A tribometer is based on the principle of the ball on three plates principles, which includes a ball-measuring geometry consisting of a shaft, a ball and a ball fixture (see figure.2) [29]. The ball fixture enables the use of balls made of different materials, and their easy replacement. The plate texture at the bottom part is mounted on a special designed spring system allowing motion in all directions of the coordinate system: x, y, z. This flexibility ensures the concentric positioning of the fixture to achieve a uniform force distribution from the ball onto all 3 plates. The rotational speed applied to the shaft is producing a sliding speed of the ball with respect to the plates at the contact points. The resulting torque can be correlated with the friction force by employing simple geometric calculations. The normal force of the rheometer is transferred into a normal load acting perpendicular to the bottom plates at the contact points.

$$F_L = 2 \cdot \cos\alpha \cdot F_N, \quad M = \sin\alpha \cdot F_F \cdot r_{\text{ball}}$$

with r_{ball} being the radius of sphere and α the angle of the plates, respectively. The following dimensions have been used: $\alpha = 45^\circ$, $r_{\text{ball}} = 12.7/2 \text{ mm} = 6.35 \text{ mm}$.

Figure 2: Schematic representation of the ball on three-plates-device

Prior to the friction tests, the samples or tribopairs were ultrasonically cleaned using isopropanol, followed by rinsing with Petroether and air dried. Experiments were performed under pure sliding conditions in a ball (100 Cr6, G-28) on three plate device (Anton Paar), by keeping the plates stationary and rotating the ball at a wide range of sliding speeds up to 1.4m/s. The temperature was stabilized at 25°C using a Peltier and the normal load was fixed at 20 N. For each test a new ball was used. Poly-alpha-olefin with different viscosities was used as a lubricant for these test, which includes PAO for low viscosity (Type 1) at 39.5 mm²/s at 20°C and PAO for high viscosity (Type 3) at 1300 mm²/s at 40°C. 1µl poly-alpha-olefin (PAO) without additives (base oil: Isoflex Topas L32) was distributed on each plate at the point of the tribocontact with µ-Pipette during each test.

The measurement process was divided into two stages, the initial stage provides three stribek curves after a first quarter of an hour and the final stage provides, another three stribek curves with an interval of an hour from first quarter. The friction coefficient, μ , was recorded every second during the test. All friction data are averages of the six measurements or stribek curves for each type of geometry. The morphologies of the surfaces were characterized by LEXT OLS4000- Industrial Laser Confocal Microscopes 3D and Leica DM4000 M for Material Analysis.

Hertzian contact length and Hertzian contact pressure was calculated for the textured and un-textured samples with respect to the ball. Contact pressure measurement was performed with a

medium range Fujifilm pressure measurement foil, which gives the point of pressure from 10 to 50 MPa. These foils were installed on the samples tested for the contact pressure measurements. Test were performed under the normal load of 20N, without using any lubricant within a static condition for a maximum duration of 10 minutes. After each test, the area of the contact pressure was examined by using Leica DM4000 M for Material Analysis and Fujifilm Pressure Distribution Mapping system (FPD-8010E). Effects of the temperature change was also studied by using a designed temperature loop programme for the polished samples under an applied load of 20N, with a low viscosity lubricant (PAO). The recorded data was used for the study the effect of the temperature on the friction coefficient and morphology of surfaces was examined by LEXT.

3. Results and Discussion

Figure 3 and Table 2 summarized the evolution of the friction coefficient, μ , as a function of the sliding velocity, u . Textured geometries were tested under the same conditions with a lubricant of two different viscosities. Friction measurements were taken over a wide sliding range while progressively increasing the speed from 0.0094 m/s to 1.4 m/s. Low viscosity experiments (Type 1) were performed to see the effect of different textured geometrical pattern in the mixed regimes and High Viscosity experiments (Type 3) were focused upon the transition from boundary to hydrodynamic regime.

Figure 3: Friction coefficient, μ , vs. sliding velocity, u
(Type 1,3: Low viscosity and High Viscosity)

3.1. Contact length effect

During the transitions from the boundary to the mixed regime, It can be seen that the leading edge of all texture shape is introducing friction reduction while the trailing edge promote friction increase, this is due to abrupt increase in the film thickness, which is in agreement with

the literature [1]. It is quite interesting, to observe the trend of the friction reduction in the rectangular geometry during the mixed regime. Among, all of the tested geometries, the samples textured with a rectangular geometry has highest friction reduction at the leading edge with an increase in the sliding velocity and it shows similar trend during both experiments until it reaches to the sliding velocity of 0.01m/s. The possible reason for this behaviour could be the contact length between the textured surface and the ball. As, we know that smaller the contact length means higher the stress and lesser the friction. Rectangular geometry has a smaller contact length among all geometries, due to which, it has a smaller contact area and the higher stress concentration at the edges of the textured surface. This lead to reduction in the friction with an increase of a sliding velocity in the mixed regime, but, it also causes a decrease in the load bearing capacity during this regime.

Usually, the friction coefficient of the asperity contact (mixed regime) is much higher than that of full-film lubrication. As a result, the higher the load- carrying capacity of a texture, the less the load is supported by the asperity contact. Hence, the asperity contact contributes less to friction force, resulting in a lower friction coefficient. This is why the optimal texture shape obtained from maximum load-carrying capacity is also capable of producing a low friction coefficient. Our results are in agreement with the literature [3,4,5,11]

3.2. Alignment effects (quasi rectangles)

It is interesting to observe that the parallel alignment of the textured samples with respect to the sliding direction, shows a positive trend in the friction during the point contacts. This is fully contradicting to the literature [1,6], which expect to show a negative trend instead of positive trend during this type of alignment against sliding direction in sliding contacts [11,21]. An experimental confirmation of our results shown in figure.2 & table.2. This could be considered as a benchmark for further studying the impact of the direction of alignment with sliding direction for the point contacts.

An experimental confirmation of our results shown in fig.2 & table.2. Which shows that all of the samples were aligned parallel to the sliding direction for both experiments. Type 1 experiment shows a better friction reduction in the mixed regime as compared to the un-textured samples (polished). Type 3 experiment, shows a reduction in friction with increase in sliding velocity at the leading edge but, the polished samples show more reduction close to interface of the Mixed and EHL regime.

Table 2: Industrial Laser Confocal Microscopes 3D Images

Textured Geometry	Optical micrograph for low viscosity	Optical micrograph for High viscosity
Hexagonal		
Triangular		
Rectangular		

3.3 Density and Depth effect

Figure 2 and table 1, shows the effects of the textured density on the friction reduction with different geometrical patterns. It can be seen that the rectangular samples with a highest density, provides a maximum friction reduction at the low sliding velocity (until 0.01m/s) during point contacts. Triangular and hexagonal geometries follow the same trends at low sliding velocity within this regime. It clearly states that high density textured samples are beneficial for friction reduction at low sliding velocity within the mixed regimes for point contacts. It contradicts with the literature [6, 7], which provides higher friction reduction with the lower density textured during sliding contacts. It also gives us a new aspect of understanding that density doesn't behave similar in the point and sliding contacts. Depth of the textured samples also plays a vital role in the friction reduction. It has been noticed that the textured samples with a higher depth generates the micro-hydrodynamic lift at a much faster rate as compared to the other textured sample, with an increase in the sliding velocity. It shows that the high density of the textured sample with a deep depth provides a highest friction reduction at low sliding velocity or until the sliding velocity reaches upto 0.01m/s. Also, the possible reason for the triangular samples to show a highest friction reduction at high sliding velocity for low viscosity experiment due to slow generation of the micro-hydrodynamic lift due to smaller depth of the micro-holes, as compared to the rectangular geometry. It shows the significance of the depth in the rate of the generation of hydrodynamic lift with an increase in the sliding velocity.

Untextured (polished) samples show a different behaviour during both experiments. During high viscosity experiments, it shows a better reduction at high sliding velocity as compared to the textured samples. The possible reason is due to no contact between the asperities among two mating materials due to a very thick layer between them and also, the higher viscosity lubricant will take longer to be squeezed out. Also, for deep holes, the friction coefficient of the textured surfaces may even become higher than the un-textured due to the formation of eddy-like flows at the bottom of the textured surfaces, which dissipate part of the energy. This was never happened in a case of polished samples, during the high viscosity test due to which it shows higher reduction in friction. As it is in agreement with the comment of the literature [4, 11,18] but still the density concept is in disagreement with the literature and it works in our case.

3.4 Cavitation & Viscosity effect

Depending on the lubrication regime and on the texture geometry, several mechanisms may concur to modify friction such as the local reduction of the shear stress, the generation of a hydrodynamic lift between the surfaces or the formation of eddy-like flows at the bottom of the dimple cavities. Rectangular geometry shows an interesting behaviour at the interface of two regimes, mainly during the transition from the mixed to Elasto-hydrodynamic regime. Pressure distribution inside the dimples or cavitation could be the reason for this behaviour. Micro-cavitation within the Micro-holes causes the maximum reduction of friction at the point of transition from one mixed regime to EHL regime. Interestingly, despite the ideal conformity of the contact geometry, a pressure rise was generated at the contact inlet where an almost stepwise variation of the oil gap was encountered. This over pressure was then gradually decreasing toward the contact outlet, resulting in the formation of a cavitation zone which does not involve almost the whole conforming portion of the interaction domain. Cavity formed, when the pressure of the liquid inside the micro-dimple is less than the supply pressure, then a bubble formed inside it and bubble appear at discrete spots in low-pressure and grows quickly to larger size and suddenly collapse as they are swept into region of high pressure [3,4]. The higher depth of the rectangular textured samples, build up higher pressure inside the cavitation zone, which also results into the generation of the small micro-hydrodynamic lift at a much faster rate with an increase in the sliding velocity. The small lift is due to the thin layer of the lubricant or the thickness of the layer is not enough to avoid an asperity contact between the mating surfaces, so it mostly stays in mixed lubricated regime.

The friction coefficient under hydrodynamic lubrication is determined primarily by the shearing of the lubricant fluid film, oils with higher limiting shear strength will exhibit higher friction coefficients [8,12]. The tests performed with a high viscosity lubricant lead to formation of very thick lubricant film. Due to this reason, all of the tested geometries show a higher friction as compared to the polished samples, except rectangular texturing at a high sliding velocity in the hydrodynamic regime. It was observed that the friction reduction could be achieved at higher sliding velocity in the hydrodynamic regime by increasing the depth of textured samples because more deeper dimples would generate higher micro-hydrodynamic lift, which results into much higher friction reduction in hydrodynamic regime. The generation of a micro-hydrodynamic lift required a larger and deep dimple. But, it is important to maintain the specific fluid flow inside the dimples under the hydrodynamic regime for generating a micro-hydrodynamic lift [7,8,25]. Rectangular textured samples were having the highest hydrodynamic lift and friction reduction due to their deep textured geometry as compared to the depth of other geometries.

Textured Geometry	Leica DM4000 Microscopic Images	Fujifilm Pressure Distribution Mapping system
<p>Polished (P=25.5MPa)</p>		

Figure 4: Contact Pressure images (FPD-8010E).

3.5 Hertzian Contact Pressure Effects

The Hertzian theory of contact between elastic bodies has been used to calculate the contact length or contact area of radius (a) and contact pressure. The calculation was performed by using the specification of the two mating materials, which provides the contact length, as (a) = $73 \mu\text{m}$, with a contact pressure, $P = 8.68 \text{ MPa}$. Fig.3, shows dark red spots, which indicates the area effected by a high applied pressure and the light red spots where the pressure applied was too high and the light red spots indicates the area with a low applied pressure. Further, Hertz theory was used to calculate the hertz contact pressure for each sample. It was noticed that the numerical calculation for the Hertzian contact pressure due to a steel ball on a rectangular textured sample was almost half ($P = 12.5 \text{ MPa}$), as compared with an untextured sample ($P = 25.5 \text{ MPa}$). It shows the amount of contact pressure exerted on each sample within the calculated contact area.

Fujifilm Pressure Distribution Mapping system (FPD-8010E), was used to calculate the contact pressure at any point within the contact pressure area. The post processing of the data obtained from these tests were used to plot a mapping system, which show the pressure at different spots within a contact pressure area. It helps to understand the pressure at the leading and trailing edge of the point of contact. Hertzian contact pressure vary with the real contact length, the contact pressures were higher, when the ball was sliding just above each column of dimples, and the semi-contact width became wider than that of the ball above the gap between dimple columns. Therefore, the lubricant film is thinner for the samples with smaller real contact length above the dimple arrays, which could make total friction increase [2]. This could be the possible reason, for an increase of the friction in the rectangular geometry as compared to the triangular geometry during type 1 experiments. It also states that the rectangular geometry has the smallest contact length among all tested geometries.

Figure 5: Friction coefficient, μ , vs. sliding velocity, u

3.6 Temperature effects:

Figure 4 summarized the evolution of the friction coefficient, μ , as a function of the sliding velocity, u due to the change in the temperature under an applied load of 20N. Highest friction reduction was observed at two different temperature under the different lubrication regime, which are predicted as -30°C and $+80^{\circ}\text{C}$. The decrease in friction at -30°C , could be the formation of the thick layer lubricant due to solidify, which decrease the asperity contact. Viscosity of the lubricant also gets changed with an increase in temperature with respect to increase in sliding velocity in the hydrodynamic regime. The possible reason for a reduction in friction at $+80^{\circ}\text{C}$ is due to the decrease in the asperity contact at a high sliding velocity. It could be interesting to have a look on the impact of different temperature upon the textured ones and that could be useful for engines of trucks, which ultimately helps to work different components to work under very low and very high temperature and it also increase the life time of those components.

4. Conclusion

- Samples with a smaller contact length shows the highest reduction in the friction. Samples with a rectangular textured pattern has a smaller contact length among all tested samples, due to which, it has a smaller contact area and the higher stress concentration at the edges of the textured surface. This lead to reduction in the friction with an increase of a sliding velocity in the mixed regime, but, it also causes a decrease in the load bearing capacity during this regime.
- Parallel alignment of the rectangular textured samples with respect to the sliding direction, shows a positive trend in the friction reduction in the point contacts, which is fully contradict with the trend shown in case of the sliding contact for the similar

conditions. This could be considered as a benchmark for the future research to see the effects of the different ways of alignment of the sample in point contacts. Texturing of the geometrical pattern in a different direction is the best way to make the sample texturing parallel or perpendicular to the sliding direction. The different geometrical pattern could be designed and tested in different orientations upon the samples to see an impact of the sliding and orientation under the lubrication regime in the point contact conditions.

- High density textured samples are beneficial for the friction reduction at low sliding velocity in the mixed regimes for a point contact tests, whereas the highly dense samples for a sliding contacts show a negative trend, which is fully contradict to the point contacts tests. The beneficial effect of micro-dimples becomes larger with a combination of an increase in dimple depth and textured density, which causes the generation of the micro-hydrodynamic lift at a much faster rate under the different lubrication regimes. Rectangular geometry shows a faster lift as compared to other tested samples, it was due to the best combination of the density and deeper depth. It will be beneficial to textured new samples with a different density (void) to see the effects of the change in the friction in point contact.
- Cavitation pressure plays a vital role in defining the rate of the generation of the micro-hydrodynamic lift. It was found that tribological behaviour depends on the depth of the micro-dimples as well as on the dominant lubrication mode (operating conditions). The higher depth of the textured samples, build up higher pressure inside the cavitation zone, which result into the generation of the hydrodynamic lift at a much faster rate as compared to shallow dimples. Rectangular textured samples were having the highest hydrodynamic lift and friction reduction due to their deep textured geometry as compared to the depth of other geometries.
- Hertzian contact pressure for a rectangular textured sample was almost half ($P=12.5\text{MPa}$), as compared with an untextured sample ($P=25.5\text{MPa}$). It shows that textured samples have lesser contact pressure as compared to the untextured samples. It also shows the pressure distribution at the different edge of the geometry, which allows us to understand the change in the friction trend due to the difference in the applied pressure at those points.
- Temperature loop was tested to see the effect of the different temperature upon the friction by using low viscosity lubricant. The lowest temperature of -30°C shows the highest friction reduction due to solidify of the thick layer lubricant, which lead to decrease in the asperity contacts. The increase of the temperature lead to change the behavior of the lubricant at high sliding in the hydrodynamic regime. It normally decreases the asperity contact, which causes the reduction in friction at $+80^{\circ}\text{C}$

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